

Workshop Proposal for I-RIM 2025

1. Workshop Title

Robotics and Emerging Technologies in Rehabilitation: The Robot as a Tool for Both Assessment and Personalized Intervention

2. Organizers

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- Marco Controzzi, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna di Pisa (SSSA), marco.controzzi@santannapisa.it
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- Christian Tamantini, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (ISTC-CNR), christian.tamantini@cnr.it

3. Workshop Format

The session will include invited talks, interactive discussions, and short presentations selected from solicited contributions.

4. Workshop Objectives and Main Topics

This workshop aims to explore the dual role of robotics and intelligent technologies in the rehabilitation domain—as tools for both objective assessment and personalized intervention. By combining robotics, sensing systems, and artificial intelligence, it is now possible to tailor interventions to the individual patient's needs, monitor progress quantitatively, and adapt therapy in real time. The personalization of robotic intervention represents a key step toward more effective and scalable rehabilitation strategies. The workshop will address the following topics:

- Robotic systems for motor and cognitive function assessment
- Robot-assisted interventions with real-time adaptability
- AI-driven personalization of rehabilitation protocols
- Human-robot interaction and motivation in long-term use
- Data-driven clinical decision support tools
- Translational challenges from lab to clinic
- Experiences from national and EU-funded projects

5. Keywords

Robotic Assessment, Personalized Intervention, Assistive Robotics, Human-Robot Interaction, Biomedical signals, AI in neurorehabilitation.

6. Tentative Program and Invited Speaker

- A. Welcome & Introduction, Workshop Organizers
- B. Fit4MedRob case reports on intervention customization (40 min)
 - a. *HR Interaction: Integration of biomarkers into Clinical Practice.* **Eleonora Guanzioli**, Ospedale Valduce, Como, Italy.
 - b. *Stepping Forward: Agilik Exoskeleton for Children with Cerebral Palsy in a Multicenter Study.* **Emilia Biffi**, IRCCS Medea, Milan, Italy.
 - c. *Assessment of fine and gross dexterity through the transport of fragile objects: the Virtual Egg Test.* **Lucia Angelini**, SSSA, Pisa, Italy
 - d. Hemi-inattention: rehabilitation and assessment through the TIAGO robotic platform. **Stefano Ramat**, UniPV, Pavia, Italy.

- C. Fit4MedRob technologies for assessment (30 min)
 - a. *Next Generation Robots: Robot-aided Rehabilitation and more.* **Loredana Zollo**, UCBM, Rome, Italy.
 - b. *Assistive and adaptive protocols for rehabilitation robotics.* **Maura Casadio**, UniGE, Genova, Italy.
 - c. *Personalized myokinetic human-machine interface for upper-limb prostheses.* **Marta Gherardini**, SSSA, Pisa, Italy.
 - D. Interactive round table involving both speakers and audience (ca. 20 min)
- 7. List of Speakers (all confirmed)**
- a. **Eleonora Guanzioli**, Ospedale Valduce, Como, Italy.
 - b. **Emilia Biffi**, IRCCS Medea, Milan, Italy.
 - c. **Lucia Angelini**, SSSA, Pisa, Italy
 - d. **Stefano Ramat**, UniPV, Pavia, Italy.
 - e. **Loredana Zollo**, UCBM, Rome, Italy.
 - f. **Maura Casadio**, UniGE, Genova, Italy.
 - g. **Marta Gherardini**, SSSA, Pisa, Italy.

8. Preferred Date

17 October 2025

9. Expected Number of Attendees

30–50 participants

10. Target Audience

Researchers in robotics, AI, and biomedical engineering; clinical professionals; physical and cognitive therapists; medical device developers; and healthcare stakeholders.

11. Workshop Outcomes

- Cross-disciplinary exchange between research and clinical practice
- Mapping of current needs and technology-readiness gaps
- A short white paper or joint statement from participants
- Collection and publication of extended abstracts
- Foundations for new collaborative research proposals

12. Plan for Special Issue or Session

We plan to organize a Special Issue on "Robotics for Assessment and Personalized Intervention" in a relevant international journal (e.g., *Frontiers in Neurorobotics*, *IEEE Transactions on Medical Robotics and Bionics*), involving selected workshop contributors. Targeted submission: within 6 months post-conference.

13. Workshop Webpage

A dedicated webpage will be available at:

[https://fit4medrob-workshop.github.io/workshop_Fit4MedRob_IRIM25/].

It will contain updates, call for abstracts, speaker list, and contact information.

14. Notes on Registration

The two free one-day registrations will be used for invited speakers from academia and clinical institutions. Additional speakers will be informed to register independently, at least with a one-day pass.

Endorsements

This workshop is held under the patronage of **FIT4MEDROB – Future and Innovation Technologies for Medical Robotics** (<https://www.fit4medrob.it/>) funded by MUR within the Piano Nazionale Complementare PNC00000007